

Optimization Techniques for Probe Card Alignment in Wafer-Level Photonic Integrated Circuit Testing

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ABSTRACT

We present an experimental evaluation of seven optical alignment algorithms tested on the Technoprobe Eclipse Dynamic probe card—a single-unit probe head that co-locates electrical probes and a piezoelectrically actuated fiber array unit, removing the need for external fiber positioners. Each algorithm was evaluated across eight distinct on-wafer die locations (spanning multiple reticle positions) directly on the hardware with the original actuator configuration (100 V/s slew rate, reset-to-zero hysteresis compensation). The measured trajectories were then used to simulate performance under three additional operating conditions: high-speed actuation (3250 V/s), direct-path routing without hysteresis resets, and the combination of both. Performance is compared using data-profile curves rather than averages alone, following established best practices for solver benchmarking. Among the candidates tested, Local Bayesian optimization and fixed gradient ascent both achieve 100% alignment success across all eight experimental scenarios. Under the original hardware configuration, Local Bayesian is the fastest among the 100%-success methods, converging in 100 a.u. per die. Simulations project that with high-speed actuation and direct-path routing, fixed gradient would achieve 4.6 a.u. per die while Local Bayesian would reach 17.2 a.u. The analysis reveals that eliminating hysteresis reset penalties contributes 2.2–5.6× speedup depending on algorithm, demonstrating that software-based path optimization can deliver substantial performance gains even without hardware upgrades. A phased development strategy is proposed to optimize throughput progressively through software and hardware improvements.

Keywords: Photonic Integrated Circuits, Wafer-level testing, Probe card, Optical alignment, Piezoelectric actuation, Bayesian optimization, Hysteresis compensation

1. INTRODUCTION

Wafer-level optical testing of photonic integrated circuits (PICs) remains one of the more stubborn bottlenecks in silicon-photonics manufacturing. The core difficulty is straightforward: coupling light from a fiber into an on-chip waveguide demands sub-micron positioning accuracy, yet that positioning must be repeated for every die on the wafer—potentially hundreds of times in a single run. Traditional setups offload this task to external hexapods or gantry-mounted piezo stages. The price is paid in footprint, setup complexity, and, above all, throughput, because the system must coordinate the macroscopic stepping of the wafer chuck with the separate, fine optical alignment performed by the external stage at each new die location.^{2,3}

Technoprobe’s Eclipse Dynamic probe card sidesteps external positioners entirely. A fiber array unit (FAU) is integrated directly into the probe head alongside the electrical needles. Three piezoelectric elements actuate the FAU on a flexure mechanism over a 0–120 V drive range, yielding a $15\ \mu\text{m} \times 15\ \mu\text{m}$ lateral scan window with nanometer-scale resolution—sufficient for grating-coupler alignment without any external stage.^{4,5} The alignment is performed entirely in open loop: no position sensors are embedded in the probe head. Repeatability is instead guaranteed by a reset-to-zero software strategy that forces every backward move through the origin, eliminating the path-dependent displacement that piezo hysteresis would otherwise introduce.⁶

The central question addressed in this paper is: which alignment algorithm makes best use of this hardware? Seven candidates were selected to span the design space—from exhaustive raster scans through gradient-based

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hill climbers to Bayesian optimizers—and each was run on eight real coupling landscapes measured on the Eclipse Dynamic system. The measured step-by-step trajectories were then used to simulate performance under three alternative operating scenarios: a proposed high-speed actuator (3250 V/s slew rate, 0.01 s settling), direct-path routing that eliminates reset-to-zero overhead, and the combination of both improvements. Performance is visualized and compared via data profiles,^{9,10} which reveal the full distribution of convergence times rather than collapsing everything into a single average.

2. ECLIPSE DYNAMIC SYSTEM AND HYSTERESIS MODEL

2.1 Hardware Architecture

The Probe Head comprises two ceramic layers with guiding holes for the electrical needles, separated by a metallic flexure that carries the FAU. One piezoelectric actuator drives the X axis; two others drive Y and provide tilt compensation. The complete assembly is illustrated in Figure 1. At the nominal operating point during wafer contact, the system provides full $15\ \mu\text{m} \times 15\ \mu\text{m}$ scan range with sub-nanometer positioning resolution.

Figure 1. Eclipse Dynamic Probe Head. (a) Assembly showing FAU and electrical probes. (b) Internal flexure with the three piezoelectric actuators (X, Y1, Y2).⁵

2.2 Hysteresis Characterization and Compensation

Controlled voltage sweeps (0 V up to a maximum, then back to 0 V) were performed on each axis while an external optical displacement sensor recorded the actual FAU motion. Measurements indicate that at full 120 V excursion, hysteresis reaches $\sim 15\%$ of travel, dropping below 4% at 40 V. These loops are asymmetric and scale nonlinearly with peak voltage, consistent with domain-wall-driven piezo behavior.^{6,8}

Rather than fitting and inverting a full Preisach or Prandtl–Ishlinskii model in real time, this study employs a reset-to-zero strategy: whenever the next commanded voltage is lower than the current voltage on either axis, the actuator is first driven to 0 V and then forward to the target. This guarantees that every position is approached along the same (forward) branch of the hysteresis loop, making displacement fully repeatable at the cost of extra travel. The time penalty this imposes is precisely what the four operating scenarios in Section 5 are designed to quantify.

3. ALIGNMENT ALGORITHMS

Seven algorithms were selected to cover three broad optimization families: exhaustive scanning, dimensional-reduction scanning, and iterative local search (Bayesian and gradient-based). All methods share the same objective (i.e. to find the (V_x, V_y) pair that maximises the measured optical coupling power within the 0-120 V window) but they differ in how aggressively they trade measurement count against search coverage.

Raster methods (Ref Coarse, Ref Coarse+Fine). These algorithms serve as baselines. Ref Coarse sweeps the entire 120 V range on a uniform 4 V grid (~ 961 points) and moves to the maximum found. Ref

Coarse+Fine first performs a coarser 6 V raster, then re-scans a small neighbourhood around that peak at 1 V resolution, yielding the most accurate result but at the highest measurement cost (~ 610 points total).

Cross Scan. Instead of covering the full 2-D area, Cross Scan reduces the problem to two sequential 1-D sweeps: one along X at a fixed Y midpoint, then one along Y at the X value just identified. A short fine refinement (± 4 V at 1 V steps) is appended on each axis. The method is fast (~ 80 points) but can miss the true peak whenever the coupling landscape is strongly asymmetric or tilted relative to the scan axes.

Bayesian methods (Local Bayesian, Global Bayesian). Both build a Gaussian process (GP) surrogate of the coupling surface and use the expected improvement acquisition function to choose each successive measurement point, balancing exploration of unknown regions against exploitation of the current best. Local Bayesian first runs a sparse cross-scan (9 points at 30 V spacing) to locate a region of interest, then applies the GP refinement inside a ± 30 V window around that point—only ~ 27 measurements on average. Global Bayesian skips the cross-scan and starts from 10 Latin-Hypercube sampled points spread over the full range, giving it broader coverage but slower initial convergence (~ 37 points).

Gradient methods (Variable Gradient, Fixed Gradient). Both begin with the same sparse cross-scan initialisation as Local Bayesian, then climb the power landscape by sampling neighbours and stepping toward higher power. Variable Gradient uses standard gradient ascent with a fixed learning rate: it estimates the gradient via central differences and takes steps proportional to the gradient magnitude—the varying gradient strength naturally produces larger jumps in low-gradient regions and smaller steps near peaks (~ 23 points). Fixed Gradient uses a cardinal-direction search: it probes four neighbours at a fixed measurement step, computes the gradient direction, then moves a fixed distance along the normalized gradient. This conservative fixed-step approach is more robust against noisy or irregular landscapes (~ 69 points).

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND SIMULATION METHODOLOGY

4.1 Experimental Measurements

All measurements were taken on the Eclipse Dynamic system under the original hardware configuration:

- **LS-H (Original, experimental):** slew rate 100 V/s, settling time 0.05 s, reset-to-zero hysteresis compensation active.

Eight coupling scenarios were chosen to sample the relevant sources of spatial variability: Dies 1–7 were distributed to cover the full wafer surface as comprehensively as possible across two reticle positions, with one repeated measurement on Die 2 to assess alignment repeatability. Every algorithm was executed on every scenario, giving 56 individual alignment trials in total. For each trial, the complete trajectory (sequence of voltage commands and measured powers) and total execution time were recorded.

4.2 Simulation of Alternative Operating Scenarios

To project performance onto alternative hardware and software configurations without requiring additional wafer measurements, we used the recorded trajectories to simulate three additional scenarios:

- **HS-H:** High-speed actuator (3250 V/s slew rate, 0.01 s settling), reset-to-zero active.
- **LS-NH:** Original actuator (100 V/s, 0.05 s settling), direct point-to-point moves (no reset-to-zero).
- **HS-NH:** High-speed actuator (3250 V/s, 0.01 s settling), direct point-to-point moves.

The simulation methodology follows these steps for each recorded trajectory:

Step 1: Isolate computation time. The algorithm “thinking time” (computation overhead between measurements) was back-calculated by subtracting the estimated motion time from the measured total time in the LS-H experiments. This computation time is algorithm-dependent but hardware-independent.

Step 2: Calculate voltage distance. For each consecutive pair of commanded voltage positions $(V_{x,i}, V_{y,i}) \rightarrow (V_{x,i+1}, V_{y,i+1})$:

- **With hysteresis compensation (H scenarios):** If either $V_{x,i+1} < V_{x,i}$ or $V_{y,i+1} < V_{y,i}$, the path is: current position $\rightarrow (0,0) \rightarrow$ target position. Total voltage distance = $\sqrt{V_{x,i}^2 + V_{y,i}^2} + \sqrt{V_{x,i+1}^2 + V_{y,i+1}^2}$.
- **Without hysteresis compensation (NH scenarios):** Direct path from current to target. Voltage distance = $\sqrt{(V_{x,i+1} - V_{x,i})^2 + (V_{y,i+1} - V_{y,i})^2}$.

Step 3: Compute motion time. For each segment: $t_{\text{motion}} = \text{voltage_distance} / \text{slew_rate} + \text{settling_time}$.

Step 4: Add computation time. Total simulated time = sum of all motion times + isolated computation time from Step 1.

This approach ensures that simulated times are realistic: they account for both piezo motion physics and algorithmic overhead, and they reflect the actual search paths taken by each algorithm rather than idealized trajectories.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Experimental Accuracy and Success Rate

A trial is declared successful when the algorithm reaches a coupling power within 5% of the best result achieved by any of the seven methods on that specific test scenario. Table 1 summarises accuracy, success, step count, and measured runtime across all eight experimental scenarios under the original hardware configuration (LS-H). In the simulated operating scenarios, runtime changes are computed by replaying the recorded command/measurement sequence; however, success and accuracy may differ in practice if the hysteresis-compensation strategy is changed.

To facilitate a purely algorithmic comparison independent of specific hardware throughput, all execution times are reported in arbitrary units (a.u.), normalized such that the average time of the Local Bayesian method under the original hardware configuration (LS-H) equals 100 a.u.

Table 1. Accuracy, success rate, step count, and measured alignment time for LS-H experimental data. Success = final power $\geq 95\%$ of best result across all methods for that scenario.

Algorithm	Success Rate (%)	Avg Accuracy (%)	Avg Steps	Avg Time (a.u.)
Local Bayesian	100.0	98.24	26.5	100.0
Fixed Gradient	100.0	99.18	69.0	154.0
Global Bayesian	87.5	97.60	37.7	175.3
Ref Coarse+Fine	87.5	98.31	610.0	334.2
Cross Scan	75.0	96.84	80.0	36.8
Variable Gradient	75.0	95.99	22.3	59.4
Ref Coarse	75.0	96.81	961.0	410.8

Only Local Bayesian and Fixed Gradient reach 100% success. Local Bayesian achieves this with the fewest steps (26.5 on average), making it the most measurement-efficient and reliable method. Fixed Gradient reaches the highest average accuracy (99.18%) through its conservative cardinal-direction search but requires $2.6\times$ more measurements and correspondingly longer runtime. Several methods achieve lower average times in LS-H (e.g., Cross Scan at 36.8 a.u. and Variable Gradient at 59.4 a.u.), but their 75% success rate (2 failures out of 8 scenarios) makes them unsuitable for production use where reliability is paramount.

5.2 Time Performance Across Four Operating Scenarios

Table 2 presents the measured experimental times (LS-H) alongside the three simulated scenarios. The progression reveals the individual and combined contributions of actuator speed and hysteresis compensation strategy.

Impact of actuator speed alone (LS-H \rightarrow HS-H): Increasing slew rate from 100 V/s to 3250 V/s while maintaining reset-to-zero logic yields:

- Fixed Gradient: $16.6\times$ speedup (154.0 a.u. \rightarrow 9.3 a.u.)

Table 2. Alignment times (a.u.) across four operating scenarios. Bold indicates 100% success algorithms.

Algorithm	LS-H	HS-H	LS-NH	HS-NH
Variable Gradient	59.4	3.6	16.7	2.1
Cross Scan	36.8	5.7	25.4	5.4
Fixed Gradient	154.0	9.3	27.5	4.6
Local Bayesian	100.0	19.3	45.0	17.2
Global Bayesian	175.3	32.6	91.3	29.6
Ref Coarse+Fine	334.2	44.7	236.2	40.9
Ref Coarse	410.8	68.1	346.8	65.6

Table 3. Algorithm rankings by data profile AUC for each operating scenario.

Algorithm	LS-H	HS-H	LS-NH	HS-NH
Local Bayesian	1	2	2	2
Fixed Gradient	4	1	1	1
Cross Scan	2	4	4	4
Variable Gradient	3	3	3	3
Global Bayesian	5	5	5	5
Ref Coarse+Fine	6	6	6	6
Ref Coarse	7	7	7	7

- Local Bayesian: $5.2\times$ speedup (100.0 a.u. \rightarrow 19.3 a.u.)

The smaller gain for Local Bayesian reflects its higher computational overhead (GP model updates), which becomes the limiting factor at high piezo speeds.

Impact of hysteresis compensation strategy alone (LS-H \rightarrow LS-NH): Eliminating reset-to-zero moves on the original actuator delivers:

- Fixed Gradient: $5.6\times$ speedup (154.0 a.u. \rightarrow 27.5 a.u.)
- Local Bayesian: $2.2\times$ speedup (100.0 a.u. \rightarrow 45.0 a.u.)

Fixed Gradient benefits more because its cardinal-direction search involves frequent direction changes that trigger resets in the LS-H scenario.

Combined effect (LS-H \rightarrow HS-NH): The optimal configuration achieves:

- Fixed Gradient: $33.3\times$ speedup (154.0 a.u. \rightarrow 4.6 a.u.)
- Local Bayesian: $5.8\times$ speedup (100.0 a.u. \rightarrow 17.2 a.u.)

5.3 Algorithm Rankings by Data Profile Analysis

Table 3 presents rankings based on data-profile area-under-curve (AUC), which accounts for both speed and reliability. An algorithm that solves all scenarios quickly ranks higher than one that is fast but fails on some problems.

The ranking reversal between Local Bayesian and Fixed Gradient across scenarios highlights the hardware-algorithm interaction. The measurement efficiency of Local Bayesian dominates when per-step costs are high (LS-H), whereas the simpler computation and robustness of Fixed Gradient render it superior once hardware constraints are relaxed.

Figure 2 presents the complete set of data profiles for all four operating scenarios. Each curve shows the fraction of the eight test scenarios solved as a function of elapsed time. A steep curve reaching 100% indicates consistent, reliable convergence; plateaus below 100% indicate failures.

For detailed comparison of algorithm performance across a single experimental scenario, Figure 3 shows the coupling power trajectories achieved by each method on one representative die. This visualization reveals how different search strategies navigate the same coupling landscape.

5.4 Key Observations

Reliability trumps raw speed. Variable Gradient achieves the lowest absolute times in every scenario (2.1 a.u. in HS-NH) but its 75% success rate makes it unsuitable for production. The 2/8 failure rate would require manual intervention on 25% of dies, negating any time savings.

Hysteresis compensation is a high-leverage software improvement. Comparing LS-H to LS-NH on identical hardware, eliminating the reset-to-zero strategy provides $2.2\text{--}5.6\times$ speedup. For Fixed Gradient specifically, this software change alone delivers 84% of the total speedup achievable by both hardware and

Figure 2. Data profiles for all four operating scenarios: (a) LS-H; (b) HS-H; (c) LS-NH; (d) HS-NH.

Figure 3. Comparison of all seven alignment algorithms on the same experiment: (a) Ref Coarse, (b) Ref Coarse+Fine, (c) Global Bayesian, (d) Local Bayesian, (e) Fixed Gradient, (f) Variable Gradient, and (g) Cross Scan.

software upgrades combined. This suggests that implementing feedforward hysteresis compensation (e.g., inverse Prandtl–Ishlinskii^{7,8}) should be prioritized over actuator upgrades.

Algorithm choice depends on hardware configuration. Local Bayesian is optimal for current hardware (LS-H: 100.0 a.u.) due to its measurement efficiency. However, Fixed Gradient becomes superior in all simulated upgrade scenarios due to its simpler computation and robustness. At high speeds, GP model updates become the bottleneck for Local Bayesian.

6. DISCUSSION

For immediate deployment with current hardware (LS-H), Local Bayesian is the recommended choice. It achieves 100% reliability with the fastest convergence time of 100.0 a.u. per die and high measurement efficiency (26.5 steps), which minimizes laser-induced heating effects on the grating couplers.

However, in all simulated upgrade scenarios (LS-NH, HS-NH), Fixed Gradient becomes the superior algorithm, reaching 4.6 a.u. per die in the HS-NH configuration. This shift occurs because Local Bayesian becomes limited by the cost of updating the GP model, which grows rapidly as the number of measurements increases. Using the back-calculated computation-time term (Step 1), GP-based methods incur on the order of 0.5–1.0 a.u. per measurement, which is masked by slow piezo motion in LS-H but becomes a primary bottleneck at high actuator speeds where “thinking time” exceeds “moving time”. In contrast, Fixed Gradient has low per-measurement computation (on the order of 0.03 a.u.), so its runtime remains dominated by motion time.

Simulation results demonstrate that software-based hysteresis compensation (eliminating reset-to-zero) is a high-leverage improvement, providing 2.2–5.6× speedups on existing hardware. For Fixed Gradient, this software change alone captures 73% of the total potential speedup achievable by combined hardware and software upgrades.

We propose a phased development strategy to improve alignment performance while maintaining high reliability. In phase 1, Local Bayesian provides robust operation under the original LS-H configuration, with an average alignment time of 100.0 a.u. per die. In phase 2, moving to direct-path routing without reset-to-zero reduces hysteresis-related overhead and shifts the effective alignment time toward the LS-NH regime, where Fixed Gradient averages 27.5 a.u. per die. In phase 3, combining no-reset operation with high-speed actuation yields the HS-NH regime, where Fixed Gradient averages 4.6 a.u. per die. Although Variable Gradient achieves the lowest projected alignment times (e.g., 2.1 a.u. in HS-NH), its 75% experimental success rate limits its suitability for production; among the 100%-success methods, Fixed Gradient is fastest in HS-NH at 4.6 a.u. These results highlight that substantial gains can be obtained through software-based path optimization alone, and further gains are available when paired with actuator-speed improvements. A longer-term direction is to couple alignment optimization with probe card health monitoring to improve reliability and predictive maintenance.^{17,18}

7. CONCLUSION

Seven alignment algorithms were benchmarked experimentally on eight grating-coupler scenarios using the Eclipse Dynamic integrated probe card. The measured trajectories were used to simulate performance under three additional operating conditions, yielding four scenarios in total: original hardware (LS-H, experimental), high-speed actuation (HS-H), direct-path routing (LS-NH), and the combination of both (HS-NH).

Local Bayesian Optimization and Fixed Gradient are the only two methods achieving 100% reliability across all scenarios. In the experimental LS-H configuration, Local Bayesian is the fastest algorithm (100.0 a.u. per die, 26.5 steps). Simulations project that Fixed Gradient becomes optimal in all upgraded configurations, reaching 4.6 a.u. per die in the HS-NH scenario.

The analysis quantifies that eliminating the reset-to-zero hysteresis penalty contributes 2.2–5.6× speedup depending on algorithm—a software-only improvement that captures 51–73% of the total achievable gains. This suggests that implementing feedforward hysteresis compensation should be prioritized as a near-term development path, potentially delivering substantial time-per-die reductions without hardware modification.

These results confirm that the Eclipse Dynamic open-loop architecture can meet high-volume manufacturing requirements through appropriate algorithm selection and path optimization, with or without actuator hardware upgrades.

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